

A Novel Context-aware System to Support Healthcare Environments

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Abstract. The possibility of offering information and functionality to users based on their context and needs represents an advantage of current technology. However, context-aware systems can be improved by extending the level of customization. Targeting on healthcare environments, this paper presents a solution, named Ubi4Health, which generates a new context-aware ecosystem for the daily life of medical staff, patients and care-home residents. Regardless of where the user is, the solution adapts the user experience, offering the appropriate interaction mechanism, interface and device at all times. In this sense, Ubi4Health provides users with the required tool in the appropriate way.

Keywords: healthcare, ubiquity, context-awareness, dui, hci.

1 Introduction

Medical staff must address complex situations [1] which involve: working with professionals from different fields; reaching agreements; performing multiple tasks; dealing with frequent contingencies that require a constant adjustment of their actions because of the dynamic nature of their work [2]; and keeping in mind several pending tasks [3]. These conditions can be improved through context-aware [4] and ubiquitous [5, 6] systems. Users can work without thinking about the system which is responsible for adapting itself to existing conditions at any time and under any circumstance. Generally speaking, context-aware systems adapt themselves to offer functionality and information that users need depending on the context. However, current technological possibilities provide a way of taking this a step further. The context offers valuable information, such as the physical capabilities of the user, which can be used to determine the most appropriate interaction mechanisms. In this sense, the distribution of multiple interaction methods across the working environment represents a good opportunity to improve context-awareness.

The distribution of interaction mechanisms is directly related to multi-device environments. The possibility to interact with multiple devices offers richer ways of interaction. Furthermore, it also helps to improve context-aware capabilities. Users can interact with specific devices according to their needs, such as mobility conditions in healthcare [7]. At the same time, a multi-device environment adds a new possibility to improve

context-aware systems by distributing the user interfaces. As users are provided with a wide range of devices, the system can adapt the interface to the hardware and to the users' context.

Taking all the above into account, the authors have developed a ubiquitous and comprehensive context-aware solution, named Ubi4Health [8], to be used in healthcare centres. The system supports different functions, concretely, staff and task management, an alert notification mechanism, and a falls and fainting detection and warning system. This paper describes how Ubi4Health generates a novel context-aware environment for users (employees, patients and residents). The main contribution of this work lies in the use of distributed interaction mechanisms, a multi-device environment and appropriate user interfaces to adapt the system to the user's context. These elements provide users with an experience that is adapted to their wants and needs, both at information and functionality level, and to the way they interact with the system. In addition, the solution provides features that allows it to be adapted to users with different needs and conditions.

The rest of the paper is organized as follows: Section 2 provides some background information and conceptual foundations; section 3 gathers some relevant related works. Section 4 provides a description of Ubi4Health highlighting how this approach improves healthcare conditions with a new technological ecosystem by providing better context-awareness. Section 5 shows the outcomes of the system evaluation. The last section gathers the conclusions and final remarks.

2 Foundations

Healthcare has become an important research field in the last decade. Indeed, healthcare environments are one of the application domains that can be more benefited from the latest technological advances.

One of the main issues in this kind of systems is to provide context-awareness in order to improve both the attention to patients and the collaboration among the health staff.

Anind K. Dey and G. Abowd defined context as *any information that can be used to characterize the situation of an entity. An entity is a person, place, or object that is considered relevant to the interaction between a user and an application, including the user and applications themselves* [9]. Concretely, in Ubi4Health and most healthcare systems, the context for the users is focused on the specific healthcare environment in which they will be. Medical staff has as context the tasks they perform (including properties such as priority or people involved), the place they are, their working conditions, devices they use, and people with whom they interact (e.g. patients, colleagues, etc.). In the case of patients, the context includes the task to be performed, their health condition, people interacting with them, location, time and the devices they use.

Therefore, it is important to provide context-awareness as an essential attribute of healthcare systems. Proof of this is the study made by Nathalie Bricon-Souf in 2007 [5] which summarizes the efforts of different research groups related to context-awareness in healthcare environments. As a result, many systems have been proposed with a wide variety of objectives: communication between medical staff; context-awareness applied to beds located at medical centres with the capability to offer specific information; communication systems based on the user's location (including the capability to initiate videoconferences under adequate conditions); messaging systems between medical staff with contextual information; systems to control medication; tasks reminders; etc.

Considering these aspects of context-awareness, the system we have developed has as a main objective to adapt the functionality, data and interaction to that context. As a result, the system offers a context-aware environment for medical staff and patients adapted to the dynamic conditions that characterize these environments. Despite the suitability of using context-awareness in healthcare, some problems arise [5]. Firstly, *the system should be understandable and clear* to cope with the unpredictable behavior of people [10]. For example, if a system does not provide as clear as possible the updated information at any time, it is possible to generate mix-ups or unexpected situations. The second remarkable problem is the way people create new mechanisms or make use of given tools. The intent of suggesting determined behaviors through context-awareness is complex so it is better to apply it to correct bad habits [11]. In addition, it is advisable to offer users simple structures to be adapted by them. Finally, the third problem is the *possible deviations from the real use for which the tool has been developed*. An example is the consideration of the users' current status. The initial usefulness of knowing the current status is to notify whether the user is available or not. However, some users may misinterpret the status of other users and use this information in the wrong way generating undesired situations.

3 Related Works

Many projects, systems and prototypes have been developed by the research community to facilitate the performance of essential processes in health centres with the aim of finding new ways of improving healthcare processes through current and novel technologies. For example, there are specific R&D entities in which healthcare represents an important research field, as for instance the iMinds Research Institute [12]. In this section we analyse some works that are related to our approach to show the contributions of Ubi4Health in this field. Having into account the vast amount of existing related works, below we describe the most noteworthy ones that are more closely related to Ubi4Health.

MobileWARD [13] is the oldest related work. This system is a context-aware electronic patient record designed in accordance with two ideas: (a) to analyse the user's context

and react to it; (b) and to provide a correct interaction process via fingers. MobileWARD detects the entrance of a user in a ward and automatically displays the information related to the ward. For example, the system displays the exact location of users and patients in that ward.

Awaremedia and Awarenephone [14] are two context-aware applications designed for hospitals which use Bluetooth technology to locate employees. More specifically, the applications use a modified Bluetooth USB whose range of action is diminished due to some modifications. Awaremedia is an application developed for interactive devices. It includes icons representing each user: their image, localization, state and diary. Awarenephone is an application developed for phones with Symbian. It shows information about the tasks and location of workmates. Additionally, the system offers a communication channel for users through a message chat.

The closest related work to Ubi4health is iHospital [7]. iHospital is a smart environment for assisting hospital staff activities by trying to comply with the main requirements of a healthcare environment: high mobility, constant activity switching, the need to coordinate activities with workmates and the abundance of information. The system is an ideal representation of a highly interactive workplace, where the healthcare staff can access relevant medical information through a set of heterogeneous devices and collaborate, considering their own context. iHospital is ubiquitous and context-aware, so (1) users can access required information at anytime and anywhere; and (2) the system offers a context-aware communication system, which means that devices are used to monitor and derive relevant contextual information, such as the location of people and artefacts that users may need to complete their tasks. These are two key features as they tackle an important gap in healthcare environments: task time. Some other important features of iHospital are the following: supporting the mobile Hospital Electronic Medical Record, providing hospital tools to back mobile Clinical Decision Making, boosting the nature of multitasking and integrating the physical and digital domain.

VERA [15] is a phone-based system that increases awareness of health behaviour in taking medical decisions. The user, through an Android application, takes a photo and follows the following steps: (1) identifies the behaviour related to the photo; (2) selects or proposes the appropriate procedure; and (3) writes comments. In this way, users in a group can see other photos, analyse their behaviour, and then take the correct decision.

The related works analysed reveal the development of systems whose objective is the use of context-awareness to work with self-monitoring as part of a healthy lifestyle. For example, [16] presents a personalized Ambient Assisted Living (AAL) healthcare system that dynamically integrates data from both inbuilt and remote sensors within a life-logging application. The system incorporates a mobile application which dynamically integrates context data from the environment through a sensor network, commodity health devices and sensors on smartphones. Other remarkable example of using human's daily life data to reach a healthy life is Mining Minds [17]. This is a framework

which works with data generated from heterogeneous resources. Mining Minds philosophy -as its authors indicate- revolves around the concepts of data, information and service curation, which refer to the appropriateness, adaptation and evolution of both contents and mechanisms used for the provision of high quality health and wellness services.

Most related works offer solutions to specific needs, as Ubi4Health does with each one of the modules it is composed of. However, none of them considers context-awareness beyond adapting data and functionality capabilities. On the contrary, Ubi4Health incorporates the use of distributed interaction mechanisms, a multi-device environment and different user interfaces to customize the users' experience according to their context. In this sense, the capabilities of the system allow users with different needs and conditions to make use of it in a proper way. Concretely, Ubi4Health offers users the possibility to interact with the system by using their voice, gaze and movement of their body together with traditional ways of interaction (tactile, keyboard and mouse) and the interaction offered by the connection they use in the system: Bluetooth or Wi-Fi. Then, the system offers different types of interaction depending on the tasks to be performed and the user implied. At the same time, different devices and interfaces are involved to complete the customization for each user's context.

In addition, Ubi4Health differs from related works by the way it offers its capabilities. The system generates an integrated solution composed of different modules, each of them being responsible of a specific functionality. The modules are connected through Internet access sharing the same database stored in a dedicated server. Then, a collaborative, ubiquitous and context-aware environment for patients and medical staff in healthcare domains is generated. As a result, the functional scope increases as different connected solutions can be offered everywhere.

4 Ubi4Health: Improving and Making Progress with Traditional Context-aware Systems

Many factors may be considered when improving conditions in healthcare environments. From among them we have focused on task management, staff organization, rehabilitation, and, controlling falls and fainting. After visiting a residential care home, the authors realised that everything has to work perfectly by following specific protocols. The one-week visit consisted of accompanying the staff during their daily routine. This staff was composed of the chief of staff, a doctor and a nurse. The main aim of this visit was to carry out a visual inspection of their activities, behaviour and in general, their context to acquire knowledge about their needs and implied processes. It was a very enriching experience checking how the staff collaborated to perform certain tasks and the information they worked with. At the same time, the visit allowed us to move around the residential care home being able to observe patients' activities and daily routines. As a main conclusion, we observed that the tasks had to be tackled during specific periods of time and following strict protocols. People's health can depend on

it. In this sense, it is necessary to ensure adequate task management by taking into account its dynamism, which generates constant reorganization. A system developed to support these aspects should include context-aware mechanisms that allow employees to concentrate on their tasks, preventing them from being distracted by other organizational issues and thus, minimizing human errors.

In general, healthcare environments represent large spaces, a fact that makes it impossible to ensure that all patients or residents are always visualized by at least one employee. Therefore, it is necessary to move forward and offer new solutions. Current technology allows systems to automatically detect anomalous situations, analyse them and act accordingly [18].

Rehabilitation is another medical area that has become an important research field too. The patients usually must go to healthcare centres to perform their therapies, which have been defined previously by medical staff. For example, in the case of brain damage and neurodegenerative diseases, the constant repetition of exercises is a key factor in a patient's successful recovery. This information, based on meetings and interviews that the authors have had with specialists in this area, reveals the necessity for patients to abandon their normal daily life as they need to commute to healthcare centres. During short periods of time, this situation could be insignificant, but it could become very uncomfortable if the patient's conditions are not adequate and/or if the rehabilitation require longer time. New technological trends offer the capability to perform the therapies at the patient's home when it is preferred and always under medical supervision [19].

These aspects represent the basis of Ubi4Health, a novel, context-aware and ubiquitous comprehensive solution to enhance the working conditions of healthcare environments and specific processes related to patients. The solution has been developed modularly, and each module is related to a specific domain (Fig. 1): (1) *tasks module* to manage tasks (alerts are considered tasks with a high priority); (2) *rehabilitation module* to improve specific rehabilitation processes; and (3) *KFF (Kinect for Falls and Fainting) system* to automatically detect any anomalous situation a patient may experience [18].

Ubi4Health offers a set of functionalities to manage specific aspects in the daily routine of healthcare environments. However, the way the solution provides its capabilities comprises an essential aspect. How a tool is used can be as relevant as the tool itself. In this sense, the following subsection shows the way the solution offers its functionality and information to users, thus providing a new context-aware ecosystem.

4.1 New Context-aware Ecosystem through the Deployment of Ubi4Health

Throughout the modules and the corresponding infrastructure, medical staff, patients and residents are offered a system that adapts its functionality, information, interface and the means of interaction according to the existing context. The users need to obtain the information and functionality when they are involved in tasks requiring them.

Ubi4Health achieves this objective with ubiquitous and context-aware features. At the same time, the users should use that functionality and data in the best way according to their conditions. Medical staff working in constant movement may interact with the system through a mobile device (smartphone, tablet, etc.). In another case, if they need to interact with a desktop computer, they need to get to the computer each time it is needed. They waste time as their activity is interrupted because of the way the system interacts with them. The information and functionality is offered as a context-aware tool but not in the correct way. This situation is an example of the issues that Ubi4Health tackles thanks to the context-aware ecosystem it comprises.

The context-awareness in Ubi4Health represents a significant contribution in which three features and capabilities are used together: *distributed multimodality*, *multi-device* and the *distribution of user interfaces*. The first one is related to allowing users to be able to interact with Ubi4Health based on their physical capabilities while performing tasks. If a patient has a disease, but they can move their hands, using a mouse or keyboard is not a problem. In another case, the voice is an alternative way to interact with the system. Following this idea, Ubi4Health tries to adapt the means of interaction to the users' needs. Regarding the multi-device setting, it helps to customize the choice of device the user is in best conditions to work with, or to adapt the system to the user's preferences. And the distribution of user interfaces allows the system, in a specific situation, to show a large amount of data. The distribution of information among different devices based on different domains helps to keep the data in front of the user without losing information.

Figure 1 shows the different modules comprising Ubi4Health and the interaction mechanisms used in each one of them, that will be further explained throughout the paper.

Figure 1. Interfaces and interaction mechanisms of Ubi4Health

The system architecture (see Figure 1) represents a key element of Ubi4Health to define how the system works according to the users' interaction. This is composed of five layers offering different levels (with different treatment of the data and functionality): (1) *Interaction Layer* represents how the users interact with the system (movement interaction, voice, gaze, mouse, keyboard, touch or connection mechanism); (2) *Management Layer* receives each request of data (with or without the need of analyzing the context) or functionality each user has done through the Interaction Layer; (3) *Behavior Layer* analyses the context for those user's requests which imply it; (4) *Database Access Layer* represents the access to the database avoiding a direct access to it offering mechanisms like Web services; and (5) *Database Layer* that contains the whole set of information managed by Ubi4Health.

Figure 2. Ubi4Health Architecture

4.1.1 Scenario of use

In order to better understand the key features of the system, we present a scenario of use of the system to illustrate the functionality, utility and benefits of Ubi4Health in healthcare environments. As the system can be used by different user profiles with different needs (functionality, device, interaction mode, location, etc.), the scenario tries to offer a global vision. Then, some actors will appear whose interaction with the system will be performed simultaneously.

The proper functioning of a residential care home (as a concrete example of healthcare environment) is guaranteed through Ubi4Health with its Task Manager. This module offers the control to John (chief of staff) who can see in a desktop application (controlled by a keyboard and a mouse) distributed in a multi-display setting with three screens (Figure 3) the state of any task in progress at any time, the staff distribution within the environment and the notification of emergencies (each domain is shown in

one specific monitor). In this way, at 8 am, John begins his working day and firstly, he checks each monitor to know the current state of the system. In that moment, the KFF system (through movement interaction via a Kinect device) detects a person who have probably fainted and then, it generates an automatic alert. Consequently, John receives from the monitor of alerts, a video signal showing what is happening. As John confirms the urgency to the system, Ubi4Health assigns it to the employee in best conditions to attend the situation. This assignment is made based on the staff's context what implies the interaction with employees with their mobile devices which indicates their position (via Wi-Fi and Bluetooth), current task, capacities of the employee, etc. The staff in constant movement throughout the residential care home interacts with the system through their mobile devices. In this way, the employees constantly interact with the system indicating their position, the state of their tasks and then, indicating possible needs.

During the notification of an urgent situation, John's monitor is updated with the new warning but with the huge amount of information shown on it, it is difficult for him to be aware of the updates on the screen. However, thanks to the awareness mechanisms, Ubi4Health interacts with John through his gaze and can know where he is looking at. Therefore, when John looks again to the monitor with updated information, these updates are highlighted.

The residential care home offers a rehabilitation service for residents. For example, Louis is a person who has suffered a cerebral infarct and is doing a specific rehabilitation process. His rehab technician, Peter, has defined a rehabilitation program through movement interaction in the 3D editor of the rehabilitation module offered by Ubi4Health. To that end, Peter reproduce with his body the postures to be repeated by Louis. As he needs to be in front of the monitor, he can't use the keyboard and mouse to control the interface of the system (via web and a Kinect connected to the computer in use). The solution is using his voice as the adequate way of interaction which is captured by the same Kinect device he is using to generate postures with the body. In this case, he has designed a set of postures for Louis to train the action of getting up from a chair.

Louis works on his rehabilitation at home because of his circumstances, avoiding constant commutes to the healthcare center. The patient-oriented application of the rehabilitation module of Ubi4Health has been installed in his living room including the Kinect device connected to a personal computer. With this configuration, the patient follows the instructions of Ubi4Health (via text, and visual and audio signals) following the postures and repetitions indicated by his rehab technician. The system monitors Louis by analyzing the movement of his body (movement interaction). The set of exercises begins with a low difficulty level, but this level will increase based on the progress study defined by: (1) the information obtained during the physical visits to the patient made by the rehab technician (Peter); and (2) the stats the system gathers during the rehabilitation process what generates data accessible to Peter.

4.1.2 Multimodality

Ubi4Health includes a complete set of interaction mechanisms distributed over the healthcare environment (Fig. 1). On the one hand, the solution allows users to interact with traditional mechanisms (keyboard, mouse and touchscreen) which offer the possibility to work with tasks and rehabilitation modules regardless of the circumstances. However, there are situations in which it is necessary to make use of other interaction methods to enhance the user experience. In the tasks module there is a role named operator. This role has to control the completion of tasks, adequate staff distribution and the assignment of alerts. As a result, the amount of information to be managed is quite huge, a fact that requires the distribution of the data among three screens (Figure 3). Each of them represents a working space for each implied domain (tasks, patients or residents and medical staff). This distribution is useful as it makes it possible to show all the information to be managed. However, while the operator is attending one screen, changes appearing in unattended displays might not be perceived when looking at them again.

Ubi4Health incorporates the use of users' gaze to interact with the system. In this way, the system is able to know where the user is looking at in order to identify possible loss of information on unattended displays. The system adapts its behaviour and aspect to the user's context as it generates notifications to assist the perception of information [20]. To that end, Ubi4Health makes use of AwToolkit, an awareness mechanism which consists of a set of user interface widgets (AwWidgets) that assist user in maintaining awareness of display changes using different levels of interruptions of their current task [21].

In terms of technical details, the toolkit is encapsulated into a dynamic-link library (dll) file which, after being imported, will add the widgets as new tools in the Visual Studio toolbox. Diff Displays [21] has been the mechanism used to track where the user is looking at. Diff Displays is a system that is able to track the display the user is looking at by using a web camera in a multi-display setting. Specifically, the detection procedure is based on a server offered by Diff Displays to which Ubi4health is connected. The server is constantly sending information that indicates whether the user is looking at a specific display or not. The information supplied by the server is configured so as to know, second by second, if the user is looking at a particular screen. Obviously, in the case of having more than one screen, the server must be run for each one of them. When configured, the server constantly sends information related to the user's gaze so that it can be read by the application requiring it.

Figure 3. Multidisplay setting in Ubi4Health

Movement-based interaction is an essential element in Ubi4Health. In the rehabilitation module, the system is both a system to assist a patient in their process of rehabilitation, and a complete editor of exercises which allows the physiotherapist to design and create personalized table of exercises. A desktop application drives the user in the correct performance of their daily and repetitive exercises (Figure 4). Through different multi-modal guides users receive practical tips in every step for them to know what to do next. If there is any improper execution, the patient is warned and advised in various ways (sound, visual, etc.).

Patients do not need to wear any invasive peripheral as every movement is captured in the distance. The patient feels comfortable since the system is minimally invasive. They can naturally move similarly as they would do in a traditional rehabilitation process. However, they are still monitored and guided. In fact, they are continuously monitored and guided in real time. The identification of postures is made by using the development kit provided by Microsoft. The SDK allows the recognition of all the body joints that Kinect can identify, concretely through a class that represents the skeleton and offers an accessible way to them. Once the system obtains this class, the next step is to search for those points that are necessary to identify postures, by collecting their position in the obtained parameters. Each position is stored in a specific class composing a set of three values referring the exact position of the point in the space (x, y and z axes).

Additionally, the physiotherapist designs the set of exercises through a Web application. The exercises are customized according to the problem to be addressed in the user. The implementation of the virtual Web editor relies on WebGL (Web Graphics Library). WebGL¹ is a cross-platform, royalty-free web standard for a low-level 3D graphics API based on OpenGL ES 2.0, exposed through the HTML5 Canvas element as Document Object Model interfaces. It is important to notice that this JavaScript API renders 3D graphics within any compatible Web browser without the use of plug-ins. Therefore, the large majority of users would be able to design exercises through this

¹ Khronos Group. WebGL. OpenGL ES 2.0 for the Web. Retrieved from <https://www.khronos.org/webgl>

module through any computer with Internet connection and a Web browser. There is no need to install any other complex software and the design can be modified wherever and whenever.

Figure 4. Visual feedback given to patients when analysing their rehabilitation training through movement-based interaction

KFF System completes the rehabilitation module and continues making use of movement interaction through Kinect by continuously analysing a patient's/resident's postures. The objective is to detect falls and fainting, which is an important part of patients care (see Figure 5). To that end, a Kinect device is placed in specific areas of the residential care home to detect the patients' postures together with a personal computer, to which each Kinect device is connected. These computers contain the part of the system which oversees using the Microsoft SDK for Kinect whose main objective is the identification of each resident's posture. Next, the system uses the Web Server to communicate with employees, to create alerts and to locate concrete employees based on specific conditions. The server accesses the database which holds the current state of the system. This state allows the classification of the system as context-aware because it gives updated information about the location of each employee and the tasks they are performing. This information gives the system the capacity to know at any time who is the most appropriate employee to be warned when a fall or fainting spell occurs. Whenever the system detects these situations, the computer requests to the server a list of the people in best conditions to tackle the situation. Then, the server composes the list based on the location of the related Kinect device, the location of each employee and their current task.

Figure 5. Example of the automatic process carried out by the KFF System

The user's voice is another element of the distributed multimodality offered by Ubi4Health. The solution provides the possibility of controlling some interfaces through voice-based interaction thanks to the capability of Kinect via the aforementioned SDK of Microsoft. The voice recognition mechanism works by identifying specific orders inserted into XML files. This feature helps in those situations in which using the hands or the whole body is not possible. An example arises during the rehabilitation process. If a patient is performing a rehabilitation exercise, using the voice is a good way of controlling the system.

The distributed multimodality is completed with the way each user is in the healthcare environment. The infrastructure of Ubi4Health contains access points for this purpose which offer users connection at any physical point. These elements support the ubiquity and context-awareness of the system, making it possible to offer information and functionality regardless of the location of the user. As a result, the system makes use of an additional means of interaction with the users through the devices they work with. In this case, the user-system interaction is performed transparently.

4.1.3 Multidevice Setting and Distribution of Interfaces

The above multimodality is provided together with a rich infrastructure which generates the second feature related to context-awareness improvement: the use of a broad set of devices. Ubi4Health offers PCs, laptops, tablets, mobile phones, as well as Kinect cameras, web cameras and touchscreens. The result is the capacity to adapt the use of the solution to the appropriate device based on the user's needs. For example, the task module considers two user types with the role of an employee who has different mobility needs. Firstly, there are users who are constantly moving, such as doctors. They have to work with devices that are convenient for them to carry and which can be used anywhere and at any time. Ubi4Health offers them mobile phones or tablets. The other type of user has no need to move around. This is the case of the operator. They usually work

with a PC, with a multi-display setting. The main reason for this comes from the fact of working with a large amount of information from different domains.

Figure 6. Example of gaze-based interaction in Ubi4Health

The last feature of Ubi4Health that is related to context-awareness is the distribution of interfaces (Figure 3). Modularity implies the use of different interfaces for different components of the solution. This fact adds another level of customization to different needs and objectives. In addition, one of the interfaces is a distributed user interface, which is the one related to tasks and oriented towards operators, as was mentioned in Section 2.1.1. The working environment and setup for the medical staff are complex factors in task performance. Most information needs to be controlled and analysed, and many changes have to be identified to react accordingly. In addition, current technology provides users with applications in which the interface requires the use of two or more devices at the same time. These conditions require a high degree of concentration in users to be aware of all the relevant information. Therefore, Ubi4Health offers gaze-based awareness [20] with gaze-based interaction, as these users have to manage large quantities of information that is shown over three monitors to support three domains for analysis (tasks, patients/residents' state and medical staff location). As a result, the system interacts with the user by identifying their gaze and detecting where they are looking at. The information needed is shown in different ways depending on where the user is looking at, what they are doing and the urgency of giving their own information. Through this interaction, Ubi4Health is able to detect changes in unattended displays and show them to users when they look back again at those displays. In addition, the system can show videos of something happening in the medical center, for example a possible urgency detected by the KFF system, and stop the video when the user looks at another screen (see Figure 6).

5 System Evaluation

We have performed the evaluation of Ubi4Health by assessing the different modules it is composed of. In this section, we summarize the main outcomes of these assessments that in all cases were very positive.

The evaluation results of the multi-display system (see Figure 3) developed in the Task Manager module to improve the awareness of new information appearing in the screen, shows a considerable increase in user awareness in comparison to the same application

implemented without our awareness mechanism. The assessment was performed as a within-subjects evaluation with 12 participants who worked with two versions of Ubi4health. The first version incorporated the awareness mechanisms, while the second did not. Five participants were female and seven were male with an average age of 36; the oldest participant was 48 and the youngest was 21. The evaluation was based on the performance of four tasks that each user had to complete using the two versions of Ubi4health.

Figure 7. Average accuracy obtained during the evaluation of Ubi4Health with awareness mechanisms (blue) and without (red).

Figure 7 shows the outcomes of the evaluation indicating a clear improvement when using the awareness mechanisms introduced in Ubi4Health [21].

Regarding the evaluation of the Falls and Fainting detection module, we performed it with fifteen users [19]. Six users were female and the other nine were male with an average age of 31; the oldest participant was 40 and the youngest was 23. Only two participants had previously worked with Kinect. The evaluation was based on the performance of twenty tasks representing some of the main postures (*standing on*, *lying*, *sitting*, and *sitting and fainting*) and the transitions between them. The aim of the evaluation was to test if this system detects each position correctly, what the error rate is, and the system efficiency when performing the posture detections.

The evaluation results are shown in the following figures. Figure 8 shows the task completion rate, and Figure 9 shows the error frequency for each task.

Figure 8. Percentage of effective attempts to perform each task

Figure 9. Error frequency for each task

Finally, the assessment of the rehabilitation module was performed with five users that were not involved in any real rehabilitation process in order to discard interaction problems related to the particular motor skills of the users. This time we measured the effectiveness, efficiency and users' satisfaction when performing a set of rehabilitation exercises guided by the system. Effectiveness was measured by considering the task completion rate, frequency of errors and frequency of assists. Efficiency was measured by calculating the time needed to complete a task. Finally, satisfaction was measured with the System Usability Scale (SUS). Table 1 shows the performance results including task time, number of errors and assists needed.

Table 1. Performance results of the rehabilitation module

Participant	Assisted Completion Rate	Unassisted Completion Rate	Task Time	Errors	Assists
1	25	75	02:30	0	1
2	50	50	03:35	0	2
3	25	75	02:25	0	2
4	0	100	02:10	0	0
5	25	75	03:10	0	3
With experience					
	12.5	87.5	02:40	0	1.5
Without experience					
	33.33	66.67	02:50	0	1.67
Average					
	25	75	02:46	0	1.6
Min.					
	0	50	02:10	0	0
Max.					
	50	100	03:35	0	3

Table 2. Satisfaction results per participant

Participant	SUS Score
1	87.5
2	75
3	90
4	87.5
5	80
Mean	85.8

Table 2 shows the satisfaction results. With a mean score of 85.8 we can conclude that the users' satisfaction while using the system was quite high.

6 Conclusions and Future Work

Healthcare environments are an important research area in which to make efforts to improve working conditions. Health staff has to be able to address complex situations in which mobility, and multidisciplinary and dynamic features may appear as constraints. Under these conditions, an appropriate way to help users is to offer a system for their daily duties with the capacity to adapt according to their needs. For this purpose, this paper has presented Ubi4Health, a comprehensive context- solution for healthcare environments. The solution supports users with appropriate and necessary information and functionality based on their current context. In addition, the solution includes context-aware mechanisms to improve the working and living conditions of both the health staff and the patients. Therefore, Ubi4Health not only provides a much-needed tool, but also the appropriate way of interacting with that tool.

Based on the user's context, the solution provides employees and patients with the most appropriate device, user interface and mode of interaction. Ubi4Health provides a new

context-aware ecosystem in which users can interact with the system through movement interaction, voice and gaze together with traditional mechanisms (keyboard, mouse and touchscreen). This multimodality is accompanied by a broad set of devices (desktop computers, laptops, mobile phones, web and Kinect cameras), and also a distribution of interfaces for different components of the solution. As a result, the solution is able to offer functionality and information in different ways, a fact that implies an important advance in this research field.

Finally, there are some interesting research lines for future work connected with the context-aware scenario discussed. Currently, the authors are considering the possibility of extending the list of devices considered. For instance, wearable devices offer an interesting way in which Ubi4Health could increase its mobile capabilities and means of interaction apart from providing new personal health information that can be useful in healthcare settings.

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